

The ambiguity of seamlessness: The Skin Ego and the materiality of fashion

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the materiality of fashion and the role it plays in the continuous making of personal and social subjectivities, through the author's own experience of making seamless woven garments. Psychoanalyst Didier Anzieu's influential notion of 'the Skin Ego' theorizes the initial formation of human subjectivity based on the tactile interaction between the mothering environment and the baby. As a garment maker, the author analyses the woven surface or garment as the extension of the Skin Ego and enquires into the ways that the 'separation' from the earliest relationship and the unending attempt to repair this 'cut', might become figured in the ambiguity that is found in the seams and edges of garments. Integrating references from the fields of psychoanalysis, anthropology and cultural studies, this article suggests that the process of making and using garments – regarded as the interaction between human and material, as well as interpersonal, interaction – successfully reveals the ambiguities inherent in modern subjectivity.

KEYWORDS seamless ambiguity the Skin Ego materiality cut edge tactile

Introduction

As the membrane which serves as the interface between what is ‘outside’ and what is ‘inside’ the body, skin has a powerful symbolic function in generating metaphors for the boundaries that differentiate the self from the world, and the self from others. This metaphorical function of skin as a membrane, with an ‘inside’ and an ‘outside’, is perhaps most powerfully present in our clothing. Not only do the cultures of wrapping, shrouding, swaddling, bandaging, veiling and adorning all carry the meanings of this need to create and represent social membranes in the form of clothes, but also garments themselves are constructed through complex conventions of ‘right’ and ‘wrong’ ways of bringing skin into contact with cultural surfaces such as clothes. If skin is nature’s container for the biological body, then nowhere is the paradoxical nature of a living organ seen as an (im)permeable barrier more ambiguously present than in fashion. It is the ambiguity of seam and seamlessness that is the principal focus of this article. There is an ambiguity between skin as a system which is open, has apertures, breathes, interacts and signifies, and the idea of skin as a system which serves to define, demarcate, delineate and ‘close off’ one subject from another. The fact that skin is thereby rendered into an organ of sensory communication; of stable containment; and of a protective barrier, is a product of this ambiguity. This article brings, to the reader, a series of contentions made by a number of theorists on skin, and relates these to the process by which I have explored the meaning of these through my practice as a garment maker.

The Skin Ego: The bodily pre-ego

According to Freud (2001: 26), ‘the ego¹ is ultimately derived from bodily sensations, chiefly those springing from the surface of the body. It may thus be regarded as a mental projection of the surface of the body’. From this theory, the understanding of the skin as a sensitive expression not just of the body’s, but also of the mind’s, complexion reached its culmination in the work of Didier

¹ To avoid confusion, the terms ‘Ego,’ ‘Self’ and ‘phantasy’ used in the field of psychoanalysis are simplified to ‘ego,’ ‘self’ and ‘fantasy’ in this article, except in direct quotations.

Anzieu on the relations between the experience of the skin and the formation and sustaining of the ego (Connor 2004: 49). Following the tradition of Melanie Klein, Donald Winnicott and others, who conceptualized the experience of the skin in early object relations, Anzieu focuses on the mapping of early psychic experience based on that of the skin, and the development of the self in an interpersonal matrix.

Anzieu proposes the notion of the Skin Ego as ‘a reality of the order of phantasy’, which functions as an intermediary screen between the psyche and the body, the world and other psyches, and ‘provides the imaginary space on which phantasies, dreams, thinking and every form of psychopathological organization are constituted’ (Anzieu 1989: 4). The notion of the Skin Ego rests on a solid biological foundation, as it places the emphasis ‘on the skin as a basic datum that is of both an organic and an imaginary order, both a system for protecting our individuality and a first instrument and site of interaction with others’ (Anzieu 1989: 3). Therefore the Skin Ego respects the specificity of psychological phenomena in relation to both organic and social realities.

The Skin Ego is a mental image of which a child makes use during the early phases of its development to represent itself as an ego containing psychological contents, on the basis of its experience of the surface of the body (Anzieu 1989: 40). Whereas in Lacan’s theory it is the specular image that provides a unified sense of corporeal subjectivity, negotiating the opposing information received from tactile, kinaesthetic and visual perception (Gross 1991: 83), Anzieu suggests that it is the organizing and connecting function of the Skin Ego that gives the sense of corporeal unity:

The skin is a surface containing pockets and cavities where the sense organs [...] are located. The Skin Ego is a psychological surface which connects up sensations of various sorts and makes them stand out as forms against the original background formed by the tactile envelope: this is the Skin Ego’s function of *intersensoriality*. (Anzieu 1989: 103, original emphasis)

This function of intersensoriality provides the person with the sense of a unified self, without the anxiety of the body being fragmented (Anzieu 1989: 104). Through adequate tactile interactions with the maternal environment at the earliest stages, the Skin Ego builds up a self-coordinating relationship between the psyche and the soma (Anzieu 1989: 98).

The formation of the Skin Ego starts as an imaginary layer, which constitutes a biological and psychological link with the mother. Anzieu reminds us that the word ‘membrane’ derives etymologically from words meaning ‘skin’ and ‘mother’, conveying the pre-conscious notion that the mother’s is the baby’s first skin (Anzieu 1989: 13). Developing from Winnicott’s notion of ‘holding’² and ‘handling’,³ Anzieu suggests that the interaction between mother and child gradually forms the ‘double feedback system’ like an envelope, taking in the two together. By ‘double feedback’ he means that the baby seeks the attention of the adults who surround it as much as the adult seeks the baby’s attention. From this ‘mutual attention seeking’, the baby develops a successfully imitated, repeated and learned behaviour, which has a style and temperament that are the infant’s own, and these in turn become a grid which serves as a means of predicting the baby’s reactions for those mothering it (Anzieu 1989: 56).

The double feedback [...] leads to the eventual constitution of an interface, imagined as a skin common to both mother and child, an interface which has the mother on one side and the child on the other. [...] Connecting them as it does, this common skin ensures direct

² ‘In the same way that the skin functions as a support for the skeleton and the muscles, the Skin Ego fulfills a function of *maintaining* the psyche. The biological function is performed by what Winnicott calls “holding,” i.e. by the way the mother supports the baby’s body. The psychical function develops through the interiorization of this maternal holding. The Skin Ego is a part of the mother – particularly her hands – which has been interiorized and which maintains the psyche in a functional state’ (Anzieu 1989: 98, original emphasis).

³ ‘To the skin as covering for the entire surface of the body and into which all the external sense organs are inserted, corresponds the *containing* function of the Skin Ego. This function is set in train primarily by maternal “handling.” The sensation/image of the skin as sac is awakened, in the very young infant, by the attention to its bodily needs it receives from its mother’ (Anzieu 1989: 101, original emphasis).

communication between the two partners, reciprocal empathy and an adhesive identification. (Anzieu 1989: 63)

This system explains how this layer can later reappear as a flexible and empathetic psychological interface between interacting adults (Anzieu 1989: 9). This aspect is further emphasized by the contrasting nature of the intra-uterine fantasy, which is the fantasy of reciprocal *inclusion*, predominant before the formation of the Skin Ego. Anzieu adds that autistic envelopes⁴ express a fixation on this intra-uterine fantasy and the failure to accede to the fantasy of a common skin (Anzieu 1989: 63).

This imaginary space provided by the Skin Ego as an extension of skin may indicate its relevance to the formation of social and psychological subjectivities through dressing practice, as garments supplement the protective function of the skin due to human vulnerability in comparison with other animals. As humans advanced into a more developed social, cultural and moral existence, garments must have complemented social and psychological functions, too. This is evident when Anzieu points out that the skin preserves the marks of external disruptions in its form, texture, colouring and scars, while it shields the equilibrium of our internal functioning from these disruptions, ‘and through it a great deal is revealed to the outside world about that inner state which it is supposed to protect’ (Anzieu 1989: 17). Just like the skin, garments both conceal and reveal, are both superficial and profound, truthful and misleading. At a physical level, garments not only receive external influences in the form of wear and tear, but are also shaped and stained by the wearer’s body and its movement, and the way we dress is socially influenced, revealing much about the wearer.

As an ego based on the experience of the bodily surface, the Skin Ego registers and preserves tactile sensory traces. Anzieu points out that the Skin Ego is ‘like a palimpsest, the erased, scratched-out, written-over first outlines of

⁴ ‘The autistic subject rejects communication by means either of the eyes or speech, since he refuses to accept separation from the mother’s body, to accept a boundary. [...] The Skin Ego is an envelope which emits and receives signals in interaction with the environment; [...] The autistic child has a notion of such an envelope, but for want of concrete experiences to bring it into being, the envelope remains empty, dark, inanimate, dumb. Autistic envelopes thus provide a proof *a contrario* of the structure and functions of the Skin Ego’ (Anzieu 1989: 230).

an “original” pre-verbal writing made up of traces upon the skin’, which he compares to the social function of scarification, tattooing, make-up and clothes (Anzieu 1989: 105).

The baby’s development into an independent person means that this idea of a common skin is gradually suppressed, and the baby, recognizing that each has his or her own skin/ego, makes the final transition from the narcissistic relation to object-relations (Anzieu 1989: 63, 65). Anzieu quotes Sylvia Plath in ‘Ocean 1212-W’ (1979) to convey the pain and resistance experienced in the separation phase:

I who for two and a half years had been the center of a tender universe
felt the axis wrench and a polar chill immobilize my bones [...]
Hugging my grudge, ugly and prickly, a sad sea urchin, I trudged off
on my own, in the opposite direction toward the forbidding prison. As
from a star I saw, coldly and soberly, [...] the separateness of
everything. I felt the wall of my skin: I am I. That stone is a stone. My
beautiful fusion with the things of this world was over. (Plath, quoted
in Anzieu 1989: 19–20, original emphasis)

The urchin’s skin that separates and rejects contact is the acute sense of loss that Plath felt at the birth of her brother. This first wound, the separation from the mother, seems to reflect the fundamental human condition perceived as separate and incomplete, and also to foreground the continuing attempt to repair the wound by searching for empathetic links with others. This article inquires into the ways that the ‘separation’ from the earliest relationship might become figured in the ambiguity that is found in various forms of seaming, hemming and the openings and closures of garments.

In the same manner as the registering and inscribing function of the Skin Ego, the continuing ‘crises’ – separations and suppressions of the Skin Ego – inevitably experienced throughout life involve some form of markings or changes on the level of skin and garment. Without necessarily referring to the scarification performed in the rites of remote cultures, the common practices of tattooing, hair-dyeing or changing one’s style of garments all express the

increasing independence of an individual from the maternal environment, as well as their incorporation into social groups, marking a change in social identity. The notion of Skin Ego thus makes it possible to regard a woven surface/membrane as the matrix of human interaction. Almost permanently in touch with the skin, a garment is a significant part of the baby's tactile experience. Not only can its influence on the formation of the Skin Ego not be overestimated, the garment itself can also be said to become the material equivalent of the Skin Ego in later life, as explained above. A garment is therefore a social medium as well as a site of interaction, through which the development of one's individual style as a unique person is encouraged and recognized.

Transitional objects

As noted above, Anzieu borrows Winnicott's notion of 'holding' and 'handling' to explain the tactile interaction between the mothering environment and the baby within the Skin Ego, which provides the sense of a protective envelope, at the same time as allowing the baby to build up its corporeal subjectivity in relation to others. To understand the place a garment occupies in this developmental stage, it seems necessary to elaborate on this process in relation to material objects by referring back to Winnicott's notion of Transitional Objects and Transitional Phenomena and 'illusionment and disillusionment' in connection with the social function of the Skin Ego.

Winnicott's Transitional Object refers to 'the first "not-me" possession' that aids the infant's journey from the pure subjectivity to objectivity (Winnicott 2005: 8), revealing the infant's tendency to weave 'other-than-me' objects into the personal pattern (4). The growing infant evolves fantasies about boundaries revolving around the mother, the first bit of the outside world that enters the orbit of his or her awareness (Phillips 1988: 77). On the part of the infant, the mother (and her breast) evolves from the illusion of being under the baby's magical control to being a part of reality, an external object which is outside the baby's control (through the weaning process). The Transitional Object is never under the infant's magical control, nor is it outside his/her control, in the way that the mother is (Winnicott 2005: 13). The Transitional Object can thus be

regarded as the material thing which prepares the baby for the suppression of the Skin Ego, and accompanies him/her in the process. It is the essential tangible thing⁵ that provides the ‘continuity of the external emotional environment and of particular elements in the physical environment’ (Winnicott 2005: 18).

The role of the Transitional Object as the intermediate area between subject and object during the formation of subjectivity is significant in understanding not only the status of garments in the developmental process, but also in distinguishing the fundamental difference between thinking and making with the involvement of holding and handling tangible material which is in/out of control. In the intermediate area involving the Transitional Object, the infant gradually learns his/her relationship with an object that is perceived as external to self as subject, through the use of illusion and reality-testing (Winnicott 2005: 15). Winnicott suggests that keeping inner and outer reality separate yet interrelated is the perpetual human task (3), and the reality-testing through the use of illusion, which began as transitional phenomena in the early developmental stage, is repeated throughout life. It is the world of arts or religion that Winnicott considers as intermediate areas, where this task is ‘played’ safely without any real risk of crisis. Culture, therefore, is the medium for self-realization for Winnicott, unlike Freud’s view of it as the sublimation of instinctual life (Phillips 1988: 119). The arts, in other words, are regarded as one of the areas where ‘unintegration’ can safely happen, as Adam Phillips explains:

Unintegration means being able to entrust oneself to an environment in which one can safely and easily be in bits and pieces without the feeling of falling apart. [...] Winnicott insists that a capacity for states of primary unintegration brought forward into later life is a developmental necessity. [...] So for Winnicott the healthy

⁵ Anzieu offers a case study of a child who, when near to sleep, touches her eyelids, her mother’s, and her doll’s and her fluffy bear’s ear, which ‘helps her first of all to go to sleep with confidence, then to have confidence in her mother’s return and finally to arrive at a classification of beings and objects in which she can have confidence’ (Anzieu 1989: 26).

integration made possible by a holding environment is always reversible; states of unintegration can be tolerated and enjoyed. (Phillips 1988: 80–81)

For Winnicott, then, the intense experiencing that belongs to the arts and to religion is an extension of this intermediate area of experience (Winnicott 2005: 19). The making process that is documented here with the accompanying photos is, in some ways, a form of what Winnicott described as ‘transitional phenomena’, a cultural space in which the play of relating subject and object is being constructed, considered and deconstructed.

The notion of the Transitional Object indicates the importance of materiality during the phase of ‘unintegration’. It may be said that materiality allows for unintegration without the risk of it becoming disintegration, as with the material in the making process; the body scarification in rites of passage; and the role of garments in the everyday changing of identity, which I will explore later in this article. The intense emotions and sensations disrupting the cohesive self can be controlled and enjoyed by partly sharing it (if it is imaginary) with the material in contact which temporarily emerges as quasi-subject. With this tangible, grounding material that is temporarily mingled with corporeal subjectivity, the boundary between reality and fantasy can be dissolved more liberally.

[I]n fantasy things work by magic: there are no brakes on fantasy, and love and hate cause alarming effects. External reality has brakes on it. [...] fantasy is only tolerable at full blast when objective reality is appreciated well. The subjective has tremendous value but is so alarming and magical that it cannot be enjoyed except as a parallel to the objective. (Winnicott, quoted in Phillips 1988: 85)

When applied to design practice or making, reality and fantasy are tested through interaction with the ‘material’ – the *matter* that the maker interacts with, and the *body* which performs the skill or technique. The maker ‘realizes’ what can actually be achieved with the body and the material, testing the limits

of control, repeatedly challenging the edge of the fantasy of idea and the reality of materiality. It becomes evident in the process of making that what is more important than ‘what if’ is the maker’s readiness to test whether or not the idea can be applied in reality. No artist or designer suffers from a lack of ideas, but the accumulated experiences of ‘reality-testing’ as a practitioner provides them with a better sense of where the limit of their ‘chosen’ reality is, whether this limit can be reset, whether it is worth pursuing. Material is less yielding than thoughts. If making is perceived only as a joy and pleasure, it might indicate that the boundary between idea and reality has never been approached or challenged. The experience of meeting this limit is a necessarily frustrating, even painful, one, depending on how passionate the maker was about the initial fantasy. Winnicott suggests that ‘through artistic expression we can hope to keep in touch with our primitive selves whence the most intense feelings and even fearfully acute sensations derive, and we are poor indeed if we are only sane’ (quoted in Phillips 1988: 81). Making teaches where the edge is, how to approach it, and how to stay on this edge despite the challenge, as the idea or fantasy can be most enjoyed on this edge.⁶ As Philips points out, ‘development through the use of Transitional Phenomena was [for Winnicott] [...] a growing capacity to tolerate the continual and increasingly sophisticated illusionment-disillusionment-re-illusionment process throughout the life-cycle’ (1988: 121). The making process epitomizes these recurring transitional stages at a material level, and the emotional and uncomfortable sensation when facing the edge of self is also experienced in the making process.

Materiality in the liminal state

The ‘crisis’ of the subject in encountering an Other which challenges the edge of self and the intense emotion and sensation experienced during the boundary-shifting, can be witnessed in the rites of passage that human beings experience.

⁶ The concept of a ‘critical edge’ was much used by abstract and colour field painters in the mid twentieth century. Psychoanalyst Marion Milner also writes of the emotional significance of ‘edges’ in painting in *On Not Being Able to Paint* (Milner 2010).

The anthropological notion of liminality was first formulated by Arnold van Gennep in *The Rites of Passage* (1960 [1909]), in the context of rituals in small-scale societies. Van Gennep sees life itself as an expansive transitional stage where people separate and reunite, die and are reborn, in changing forms and conditions (Gennep 1960 [1909]: 189), and ‘beneath a multiplicity of forms, the typical pattern of the rites of passage always recurs’ (191). Through the threefold structure of these rites of passage – separation, transition and incorporation (11) – the crucial changes in life are clearly acknowledged. And this ‘marking’ of transition with rites is considered to aid the individual along the process: this point is accentuated by the evidence of individual deviancy which is due to the absence of rites in modern western society, as psychoanalytic case studies show. ‘These changes may be dangerous, and at the least, they are upsetting to the life of the group and the individual. The transitional period is met with rites of passage which cushion the disturbance’ (Kimball 1960 [1909]: ix).

As is the case with Transitional Objects, the materiality in transitional stages of life cushions the disturbance as well as heightening awareness of the reality. Van Gennep emphasizes the importance of concrete materiality in this process of change:

[T]he passage from one social position to another is identified with a territorial passage, [...] so often ritually expressed by passage under a portal, or by an ‘opening of the doors.’ These phrases and events are seldom meant as ‘symbols’; for the semi-civilized the passage is actually a territorial passage. In fact, the spatial separation of distinct groups is an aspect of social organization. (Gennep 1960 [1909]: 192)

If passing through the portal is the phase of transition, the preceding phases of separation include the separation of baby or child from the mother by the cutting of the umbilical cord, the first haircut, circumcision, pulling out a tooth, etc. (Gennep 1960 [1909]: 62). Therefore the idea behind cutting, piercing or splitting is the separation from the previous stage, to be incorporated into a new state via the transitional stage.

In *Symbolic Wounds: Puberty Rites and the Envious Male* (1955), Bruno Bettelheim analyses the meanings and purposes behind circumcision, which is practised in many different cultures. He suggests that circumcision, found among both the most primitive, the most highly civilized people and in all continents, must originate from profound needs, especially when it is practised by choice, unlike infant circumcision (Bettelheim 1955: 16). Through his research, integrating anthropological and psychoanalytical perspectives, Bettelheim concludes that these rituals should be understood less on the basis of the concept of castration anxiety, as postulated by Freud, but more as efforts of the young, or society generally, to resolve the antithesis between child and adult, and between male and female (Bettelheim 1955: 17–18, 44).

This can be further interpreted thus: the mutilation of bodily edges or surfaces during rituals may function as a reminder of the edge in the phase of social or biological change when social or corporeal subjectivity becomes confused and less stable. Anzieu suggests that ‘mutilations of the skin – sometimes real, but more often imaginary – are dramatic attempts to maintain the boundaries of the body and the Ego and to re-establish a sense of being intact and cohesive’ (Anzieu 1989: 20), by ‘focusing attention on their skin border and perceiving the limits of their bodies’ (Connor 2004: 57). Reflecting on Anzieu’s theory behind the self-mutilation of skin, Steven Connor pays attention to children’s fascination with sticking-plasters:

The important feature of the sticking-plaster is its edge, which both seams and seals the otherwise uninterrupted surface of the skin, marking the skin and then placing it ‘under erasure.’ It appears that the imaginatively erased wound or mark is more powerfully pleasurable than the merely virgin surface. For the child, as for Yeats’s Crazy Jane, ‘Nothing can be sole or whole/That has not been rent.’ The pleasure in the sticking-plaster makes some of the purposes of deliberate injuries to the skin in adult society intelligible. (Connor 2004: 52)

The marking of skin, then, is the means to accentuate its surface integrity as well as its integrity with the bodily ego and the body image, which ‘as a “stabilizing image” and as a protective envelope must at all costs be kept intact’ (Anzieu 1989: 32).

Focusing attention on the skin as a border in turn raises the question of the role of material objects incorporated into these rites. Just as Transitional Objects aid the baby through the process of establishing subject–object relations, ritual objects both cushion the shock of change and aid reflexive self-readjustment. Apart from suggesting that mutilations are a means of permanent differentiation, van Gennep also points to the use of temporary differentiations, such as the wearing of a special dress or mask, or body painting (Gennep 1960: 74). Victor Turner also pays attention to masks, costumes, figurines and such displayed in initiation situations, which are made with outstandingly exaggerated features, sometimes amounting to caricature. Turner sees this as a primordial mode of abstraction – by exaggerating the proportion or discolouring them in unfamiliar ways, they are made into an object of reflection (Turner 1970: 103). This draws attention to the significant roles these supplementary objects play in the phases of transition in the everyday life of an individual, emphasizing the symbolic function of clothing.

The cut and repair of the skin may be displaced into the entering and exiting through the openings and edges of garments. Bodily movement in relation to the garment is comparable to the tactile sensation on skin – putting it on, entering the space within the garment, its embodiment, taking it off – the moments when garments and the body exist in mutual influence. This aspect can be seen as being symbolically celebrated in rituals such as royal coronations, or sacred veilings and unveilings. The traditional courtesy of helping guests out of, or into, their coats on arrival and departure is also a sign of the ritual meaning of entering and departing garments. At a more fundamental level, dressing practice is a creative conflict resolution that takes place every day. The self constantly crosses thresholds, yet this is so habitual that it is not explicitly noticed by the person as such, but often experienced as an inexplicable change of mood, physical condition and so on, according to which s/he adjusts the garment. If an individual goes through transition aided by

dressing practice, the liminal interface or space between the body and garments would be the seams, edges, surface and space of garments.⁷ The seam converts the flat surface of fabric into a space into which the body enters and exists. This is comparable to the individual's passage through the openings (thresholds) of a house, which is often an essential part of rites of passage.

The seam also represents the transformation from a solitary biological person to a socially situated person. Peter Stallybrass explains, in his essay 'Marx's coat' (1998) how people of limited income in Victorian England had to pawn their clothing to get through the period in between their weekly wages: the pawning of their clothes sharply limited their social possibilities, as they could not go out while their respectable clothes were pawned (Stallybrass 1998: 195). Without appropriate clothes, we are stripped of social contact. This is the garment's function as the Skin Ego, where self and other interact, and where external contacts as well as internal responses are inscribed. Garments are thus 'the materials of self-construction, the supplements the undoing of which was the annihilation of the self' (Stallybrass 1998: 203).

In many vestimentary cultures, the edges of garments (borders, hems, neckline, collar and cuffs, etc.) are often accentuated as a liminal zone where transfer and transpositions between the 'I' and the 'other' become potent (Baert 2011: 324). Pajaczkowska and Curtis (2008) suggest that hems, collars and necklines serve as ritual boundaries between cloth and skin, culture and nature, and, as such, are materialized by a doubling of the fabric. The fold as a repetition and doubling becomes, in a collar or turn-up, a successfully negotiated transition.

Garments are the ever-present 'other' that displaces the edge of self, and the edges of this edge – seams and hems – are liminal zones that convey both potentiality and danger. Mary Douglas sees the liminal state as potentiality, as opposed to restriction or limitation:

⁷ Lacan's famous notion of 'rim', 'objet petit a', and Kristeva's subsequent development of these ideas as 'the abject' are often analysed in relation to the opening and edges of garments. As these notions conflict with the interpretation of corporeal subjectivity by Winnicott and Anzieu, I choose not to include these in the main line of this article.

Order implies restriction; from all possible materials, a limited selection has been made and from all possible relations a limited set has been used. So disorder by implication is unlimited, no pattern has been realized in it, but its potential for patterning is indefinite. [...] It symbolizes both danger and power. (Douglas 2008 [1966]: 94)

To be hemmed-in is to have restricted space or movement, whereas the unhemmed edge is at risk of fraying: the material state corresponds to the fear and panic experienced in moments of crisis when the solidity of the self is challenged with an abrupt encounter with the other. Yet the possibility that self can be disintegrated and lost is threatening yet compelling at the same time, as Victor Turner saw the co-implication of life and death, unity and fragmentation in the liminal state:

It is interesting to note how [...] logically antithetical processes of death and growth may be represented by the same tokens, for example, by huts and tunnels that are at once tombs and wombs, [...] by nakedness (which is at once the mark of a newborn infant and a corpse prepared for burial), and by innumerable other symbolic formations and actions. This coincidence of opposite processes and notions in a single representation characterizes the peculiar unity of the liminal: that which is neither this nor that, and yet is both. (Turner 1970: 99)

The power of indeterminacy implies the paradoxical interconnections between destruction and renewal (Hawkins and Muecke 2003). The photos accompanying this article illustrate a particular way in which cut pieces of fabric are put together to be constructed into garments. This seaming method – cutting through a piece of woven cloth, purposefully fraying the cut edge, and then reweaving the individual frayed threads into another cut edge of cloth – is a reminder of many tokens of cutting, passing through and connecting observed in the rites of passage. The possible affinity between the human skin and a garment formed through repeated use renders this comparison particularly

compelling. Moreover, for the maker, the process of seaming – investing ‘excessive’ time, effort and attention while being temporarily cut off from the world – is also a transitional experience. As the material held by the hands is slowly transformed through repeated touches of a needle on and through the surface of cloth, and the surface of the body (not unlike scarification or tattooing), the maker also goes through a change.

The illustrated hand-woven seams also accentuate the aspect of dressing as self-making by exposing the internal structure of the garment, highlighting the process of putting together both a garment and a self. Our appearance and subjectivity are ‘put together’, rather than emerging as an unchanging whole, and garments play an indispensable role in compensating for the body’s limitations in their calibration of the changing self. Owing to its materiality in contact with the body, the garment can reveal as well as conceal the seams of the self. Therefore, together, the seam and seamlessness represent the subject-in-process, and fashion as a particular way of being in a permanent transitional passage.

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Figure 1: 'Seamless' Woven Dress One. Front detail.

Figure 2: 'Seamless' Woven Flared Skirt. Vertical seam (in progress).

Figure 3: 'Seamless' Woven Dress Two. Side panel (in progress).

Figure 4: 'Seamless' Woven Dress Two. Front neckline detail.

Figure 5: 'Seamless' Woven Flared Skirt. Vertical seam detail.

Figure 6: 'Seamless' Woven Dress One. Shoulder seam (in progress).

Figure 7: 'Seamless' Woven Dress Two. Side view.